

NDAC/LO/118
1989 March 8

27th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory
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WP6000: Step 2/3 (Lindegren)

No work to report from December 1988 to February 1989.

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm)

The tests of the main parts of the SEEKDBL program were finished in December (C). Work has then concentrated on the important derivation of the Case History Files, which are used by all later analysis programs. An outline of the procedure has been devised, and work is in progress writing the several programs required. For the sorting of chronological data in system-order, the main routine of SORT23 will be used.

Miscellaneous (Lindegren)

The calculation of 'pseudo-variances' of the abscissae in Step 1 has been studied (C). A combination of exact calculation and statistical prediction is found to be computationally efficient and probably sufficiently accurate.

A subroutine for calculating the geocentric ephemerides of minor planets, which was sent to RGO and CUO in August 1988, has been updated to include the major planets (Venus to Neptune) and the moons J2 Europa and S6 Titan. Distribution of the new version has been delayed, however, pending clarification of certain data provided by the Bureau des Longitudes.

Working papers:

- C = NDAC/LO/116 (Söderhjelm, 1988 Dec 16):
HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VIIIb
- C = NDAC/LO/117 (Lindegren, 1989 March 2):
Calculation of abscissa variances for the Great-Circle
Reductions